

Eye-Tracker Technology For Learning Abstract Art: A Systematic Literature Review

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In recent years, the application of eye tracking technology in the field of art education has received extensive attention, especially the application of eye tracking technology in the learning of abstract art. Considering that there are already have a large number of empirical studies in this specific field, this study aims to analyze and synthesize the current research on the application of eye tracking technology in the exploration of abstract art. The research focus to summarize the research trends, current progress, key variables and eye movement indicators used in the research in the past decade. This study systematically uses the methods of systematic review and meta-analysis to organize 160 articles on the application of eye tracking technology in the learning of abstract art from 2014 to 2024. Through the analysis of five empirical studies, we summarize the research trends, current status, research variables and commonly used eye movement indicators in this field. First, the study shows that the application of eye tracking technology in the field of abstract art learning has gradually increased since 2014, especially reaching a research peak from 2019 to 2021. Secondly, the independent variables and dependent variables involved in the study are relatively diverse. The independent variables include color, shape, symmetry, golden ratio, etc., and the dependent variables include emotional areas, aesthetic judgments, motion cues. These studies show that eye tracking technology can effectively capture students' visual and emotional responses when viewing abstract artworks. Finally, commonly used eye movement indicators such as gaze position, duration, and pupil size can reflect students' attention and emotional responses. The use of these indicators provides quantitative support for understanding the impact of abstract art on students.

Key words: Eye-tracker; Abstract Art; Higher Education; Systematic Review

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Introduction

Research background

In recent years, the application of eye-tracking technology in the field of art education has gained significant attention. Research has demonstrated that eye movement patterns can decode visual information, providing insights into cognitive processes (Barnes, 2008; Salvucci et al., 2022). Meanwhile, many studies on abstract art began to apply eye-tracker as a tool to explore art appreciation. Art appreciation is inherently subjective, with viewers exhibiting varied viewing sequences and preferences. (Bowie et al., 2003; Hall, 2004) This is particularly evident in learning abstract art, which departs from realistic representation and emphasizes the use of color, lines, shapes, and texture to convey meaning and emotion (Leder et al., 2012) Eye-tracking technology offers valuable tools for researchers to analyze and understand how students engage with and interpret abstract art. The study aims to analyze and synthesize current studies on the use of eye-tracking technology in the exploration of abstract art. The primary focus is to summarize research trends, current advancements, key variables, and eye-tracking metrics employed in studies over the past decade. By highlighting the role of eye-tracker in abstract art learning, this work seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of its application and implications in this domain. The study is divided into six parts, systematically exploring the application of eye-tracking technology in abstract art learning. It also discusses the current status, trends, and specific research methods in this field. The first part introduces the research content. The second part summarizes the theoretical background of the research and the research gaps in abstract art. The third part introduces the methods and

research questions of this study. The fourth part reports the main results of this research question. The fifth part discusses the significance, suggestions and main limitations of this study. Finally, the sixth part reports the conclusions of this study and future research.

Systematic Review on Eye-tracker technology

The basic knowledge of Eye-tracking device

The development of eye movement measurement technology can be categorized into four stages: observation methods, mechanical recording methods, optical recording methods, and modern eye-tracking systems (Leigh & Zee, 2015). With advancements in technology at the turn of the 21st century, more reliable, non-invasive, and accurate eye-tracker have emerged. The Pupil Center Corneal Reflection (PCCR) technique (Shehu et al., 2021) is widely utilized in modern eye-tracking devices due to its high precision, non-contact nature, and non-invasive properties. The core principle of PCCR eye movement technology can be summarized in one sentence, "The direction of vision is determined by the position of the pupil center relative to the corneal reflection." (Zhu & Ji, 2005)

Figure 1. With constant head and light source positions, the pupil and corneal reflection shift with eye movement (Bojko,2013; Duchowski, 2007)

As illustrated in Figure 1 , the bright spot on the eye is formed by the corneal reflection, and its position is determined by the relative positions of the light source and the subject's head. If the subject keeps the head still and rotates the eyeball to look around, the corneal reflection does not move, only the pupil does. The orientation relationship between the center of the pupil and the change in the corneal reflex can be clearly seen in the figure. In the other case, the subject gazes at a fixed target while rotating the head and observes how the relative positions of the pupil and corneal reflex change. From Figure2, it is easy to see that when a subject is staring at a fixed target, the positional relationship between the center of the pupil and the corneal reflex does not change no matter how much she moves her head. Even if the subject is moving, the eye-tracker reflects that she is looking at the same location. Therefore,with the light source and head position relatively stable, data on pupil orientation can be obtained by collecting light reflected from the cornea and retina and analyzing their relative positional relationship. This is the principle of the pupil-cornea reflex ophthalmoscope.

Figure 2. The relative positions of the pupil and corneal reflex do not change when the head is moved but looking at the same location (Bojko, 2013)

It is generally acknowledged that the development of multimedia in art education reflects a shift from traditional methods to more technologically advanced interactive methods. (Andresen , 2013;Liu , 2021) The application of eye-tracker in art education is in line with this contemporary theme. There are many studies on the integration of eye-tracking instruments with art learning. Involving all aspects of art appreciation, some studies are dedicated to analyzing the differences in expertise, eye movement patterns, and visual memory between students who are art major and ordinary people in viewing paintings. (Francuz et al., 2019; Vogt & Magnussen, 2007) There are also many studies that use eye-tracker to analyze the user experience of factors such as the display layout of works in museums and art galleries, indoor lighting, and environment. (Brinkmann et al., 2023; Carbon, 2017; Yi et al., 2020) In addition, some studies focus on using eye-tracker to observe the eye movement characteristics of students when appreciating the form and painting language of artworks. (Fazlyyyakhmatov et al.,2020;Glaser&Schwan , 2015).

Many studies have applied eye tracking technology to the field of abstract art learning. The application of eye-tracker is particularly valuable in addressing the unique characteristics of abstract art, a form of artistic expression that emphasizes visual elements such as color, shape, line, and texture to convey emotions and ideas rather than representing recognizable physical objects or scenes (Schapiro, 1937). Rather than pursuing the narrative nature of images, this art form focuses on experimenting with form, color, and composition to explore different modes of perception and expression. (Leder et al., 2012) By capturing eye movements, this technology helps researchers better understand how viewers view abstract art.

Gaps in the systematic review of eye-tracker for art& abstract art

Figure 3. A distribution map of studies on the use of eye trackers in art appreciation

In the past decade, the application of eye tracking technology in art appreciation research has received widespread attention, with a total of 50 related papers published. Among them, 43 studies focused on paintings, 35 specifically studied oil paintings, and among these oil painting studies, 19 took abstract painting as the main research object. Given that abstract art occupies a considerable proportion of these studies, it is obviously necessary to systematically organize and summarize the application of eye tracking technology in abstract art appreciation in order to fully understand the research progress in this field.

Figure 4. Literature review of related fields in the context of this study

On the other hand, a considerable amount of literature reviews have focused on the eye tracking technology itself. (Alemdag & Cagiltay, 2018; Hu et al., 2022). These studies provide guidance for the application of eye trackers in various disciplines. As show in Figure 4, there are also many literature reviews in the field of art learning (Leder & Nadal, 2011; Zhao & Zhang, 2024), among which abstract art as an important art style (Alderton, 2011; Parlog, 2019) has also been reviewed. However, although there are currently three literature reviews that explore the combination of eye-tracker and art education. (Kedziora et al., 2020; Nayak et al., 2019; Ronsenberg et al., 2022), there is no review specifically for combination of eye-tracker and abstract art learning. Considering that there has been a large amount of empirical research in this specific field, especially the application of eye tracker technology in abstract art learning, which almost occupies a large part of art appreciation research, this literature gap highlights the urgency and necessity of research.

Methodology

The study presents a systematic literature review, and the researchers adopted two research methods: systematic review and meta-analysis. A systematic review aims to bring evidence together to answer a pre-defined research

question. This involves the identification of all primary research relevant to the defined review question, the critical appraisal of this research, and the synthesis of the findings. (Gough ,2017)

The research questions of the study are as shown in table 1:

- (1) What are the trends in research on applying eye-tracking technology to learning abstract art since 2014 to 2024?
- (2) What is the current state of development of research on the use of eye-tracking technology in learning abstract art?
- (3) What variables have been considered in research on the use of eye-tracker in learning abstract art?
- (4) What eye-tracking indices are used in studies on abstract art?

Table 1. Research questions of the study

	Research Question (RQ)
RQ1	What are the trends in research on applying eye-tracking technology to learning abstract art since 2015 to 2025?
RQ2	What is the current state of development of research on the use of eye-tracking technology in learning abstract art?
RQ3	What variables have been considered in research on the use of eye-tracker in learning abstract art?
RQ4	What eye-tracking indices are used in studies on abstract art?

Search strategy

As a research sample, college students majoring in art were used in a systematic search to find empirical studies of learning abstract art , abstract art belong to the category of humanities and social sciences in higher education, and will involve many factors such as culture , appreciate, math and technology. Therefore, the study used 5 databases for searching: Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, Scopus, Taylor & Francis. These papers were published between 2014 and 2024. Google Scholar is a free academic search engine that provides retrieval services for scholarly articles, dissertations, book chapters, conference papers and other resources, covering a wide range of subject areas. IEEE Xplore is a digital library focusing on electronic engineering, computer science and related technical fields, suitable for researchers looking for high-quality scientific papers and technical materials. As we all know, Web of Science is a multidisciplinary academic database that contains high-impact journals, conference papers and books worldwide. Scopus covers journal articles, conference papers, book chapters and other documents in multiple fields such as science, technology, medicine, and social sciences, and provides powerful bibliometric analysis tools. Taylor & Francis includes humanities, social sciences, life sciences, and is an important resource for scholars to conduct literature retrieval and research. The study used three sets of keyword searches: eye tracking , art education, abstract art or eye tracker, art learning, abstract art or eye movment technology, painting, abstract art , The initial search yielded 160 articles related to the keywords, of which 7 were obtained through manual search and related literature. Figure 5's flowchart of the literature review process illustrates how publications are identified, screened for eligibility, and included. The study examined the titles, abstracts, variables, samples, methods, and results of the selected studies to determine their suitability for investigation.

Figure 5. Flowchart of the PRISMA-based selection process.

Eligibility review: inclusion and exclusion criteria

To obtain papers relevant to this study from the 160 literatures, the researchers used sample, phenomenon of interest, design, evaluation, research type model (SPIDER) as a framework to formulate eligibility criteria in the study. SPIDER is a standardized systematic search strategies facilitate rigor in research (Cooke et al., 2012). This investigation used both tools to find systematic reviews and meta-analyses by applying exclusion and inclusion criteria. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria used in this investigation are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Paper published between 2014 and 2024.	Papers older than 2014.
The full paper is written in English.	Non-English
Applying eye-tracking to the field of learning abstract art.	Eye-tracking devices are used in other fields, except abstract art.
The eye-tracker is the main research instrument.	The eye-tracker is not the main research instrument.
Papers from international peer-reviewed journals.	Papers from proceedings, reports, letters or book chapters with simple abstracts

Methods

In the study, we used SPIDER as a search framework and combined the same search terms to conduct a systematic narrative review of the literature on the application of eye trackers in abstract art research. This review focused on quasi-experimental research papers rather than descriptive research papers, because quasi-experimental research is more conducive to comparisons between sample populations, research results, and research objectives.

After screening according to the pre-set criteria, we found a total of 160 articles, of which 5 were duplicated, 136 did not meet the keyword criteria, 5 were non-empirical studies, 3 were related to the art market, 3 were related to museum user assessment, and 3 were proceedings. Finally, 5 papers met the requirements, and these 5 were quantitative studies. The detailed information of these articles is shown in Table 3:

Table 3. Research papers included in this review

No.	Title	Author, date of publication	Object of study
1	An Eye Tracking Study on	Lucia et	Looking behavior and explicit preferences for

	Symmetry and Golden Ratio in Abstract Art	al.,2024	different regularities, including symmetry and the golden ratio, were investigated through four paintings by Mark Rothko.
2	What Gaze Fixation and Pupil Dilation Can Tell Us About Perceived Differences Between Abstract Art by Artists Versus by Children and Animals	Alvarez et al., 2015	To test whether participants showed different visual exploration when viewing the artist's abstract art paintings versus paintings of children or animals.
3	Reappraising Abstract Paintings after Exposure to Background Information	Park et al.,2015	To investigate whether a specific pattern of attention is essential for the knowledge-based appreciation.
4	Pupil responses to implied motion in figurative and abstract paintings	Castellotti et al.,2021	To measure student responses to implied motion in figurative and abstract paintings
5	Affective Analysis of Abstract Paintings Using Statistical Analysis and Art Theory	Sartori et al.,2014	To identify and quantify which are the emotional regions of abstract paintings

For the first research in the table 3 above, researchers (Lucia et al.,2024) chose four paintings by renowned Abstract Expressionist artist Mark Rothko and invited 36 students as participants (24.75 ± 3.71 years old) to complete three tasks: the Observation Task (OT), the Pleasure Task (PT), and the Harmony Task (HT). Eye movements were recorded using an EyeLink 1000 device in remote binocular mode with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz (mean accuracy reported by the manufacturer $\sim 0.25^\circ$ - 0.5° , spatial resolution $<0.01^\circ$ RMS). The aim was to investigate viewing behavior and explicit preferences for different patterns (including symmetry and golden ratio). The results showed that the visual scanning behavior of abstract art depends mainly on the orientation of the internal components, while their ratio is more important for the explicit judgment of pleasure and harmony.

The Second research of the table 3 (Alvarez et al.,2015) tested whether participants showed different visual exploration when viewing an artist's painting versus a child's or animal's painting. Participants sat in front of an eye-tracker and viewed the artist's painting paired with a "similar" painting of a child or animal. The results were derived from an eye-tracking data report, which, despite a common misconception among the general audience that "there is no difference between an artist's painting and a random doodle," showed that when considering preference and quality in art, non-specialists reacted differently when viewing the two types of paintings (an artist's abstract painting paired with a "similar" painting of a child or an animal), and when preference and quality in art are considered, laypeople react differently when viewing the two types of paintings (an artist's abstract painting versus a child's or animal's "similar" painting).

The third research (Park et al.,2015) consisted of two experiments, the first of which compared the before and after changes in aesthetic judgments of participants with no background in art knowledge after gradual exposure to five pieces of background information about abstract art. The results showed that participants increased their subjective aesthetic ratings of the painting after acquiring background information about the painting. Another experiment, using an eye-tracking device to compared the attentional patterns of participants when viewing paintings after learning information, whether specific attentional patterns are critical for higher evaluations during knowledge-based aesthetic appreciation of artworks.

The fourth research (Castellotti et al.,2021) measured pupil responses to implied motion (IM) in figurative and abstract artworks depicting static and dynamic scenes. Since the pupillary response is modulated by the subjective image interpretation, a motion rating test has been used to correct individual pupil data according to whether participants actually perceived the presence of motion in the paintings. Pupil responses to movies showing figurative and abstract subjects, and to motion illusions were also measured, to compare real and illusory motion with painted IM. Overall, the data show that pupil size depends on high-level interpretation of motion in paintings, even when they do not represent real-world scenes. The findings further suggest that the pupil is modulated by multiple top-down cortical mechanisms, involving the processing of motion, attention, memory, imagination, and other cognitive functions necessary for enjoying a complete aesthetic experience.

The fifth research (Sartori et al.,2014) proposed a novel approach to the emotion classification of abstract paintings. The researchers employ computer vision techniques to understand what makes an abstract artwork emotional. The aim is to identify and quantify which are the emotional regions of abstract paintings, as well as the role of each feature (color, shapes and texture) on the human emotional response. In addition, the research investigated the link between the detected emotional content and the way students look at abstract paintings by using eye-tracking recordings. A bottom-up saliency model was applied to compare with eye-tracking to predict the emotional salient regions of abstract paintings.

Results

This section presents the results of the four research questions posed in this study. First, the recent developments in the field of eye tracking technology and abstract art learning are followed to discover emerging trends. The second research question explores the recent developments in the application of eye tracking technology in the field of abstract art learning. Third, it examines which variables are currently applied in abstract art learning. Finally, the commonly used eye movement metrics in these studies are summarized.

What are the trends in research on applying eye-tracking technology to learning abstract art since 2015 to 2025?

Figure 6. The trend of art using eye-tracker from 2014 to 2024

Figure 7. The trend of abstract art using eye-tracker from 2014 to 2024

As can be seen from Figure 6, the application of eye tracker technology in art education showed a gradual upward trend between 2014 and 2024. The number of related studies reached a peak between 2019 and 2021, especially in 2021, when the number of papers was close to 30, indicating that the technology has received widespread attention and application during this period. However, starting from 2022, the number of related papers has declined, but it still remains at a relatively high level. This may be due to the fact that after the technology matures, the research focus gradually shifts to other more refined fields or the influence of emerging technologies. In contrast, the trend of abstract art as a branch in art appreciation fluctuates greatly. As shown in Figure 7, from 2014 to 2024, the number of papers published each year is generally around 1 to 2, with the highest peak occurring between 2019 and 2024, indicating that this field may still be in the development stage and still has certain research potential in the future.

What is the current state of development of research on the use of eye-tracking technology in learning abstract art?

From 2014 to 2024, the number of related studies fluctuated greatly, especially from 2019 to 2024, the number of studies increased significantly. This shows that although the research in this field is relatively new, the application of eye tracking technology in abstract art appreciation has gradually attracted more and more attention over time. Nevertheless, overall, research in this field is still in the development stage and has not formed a continuous and stable research output. This trend highlights the potential and challenges of eye tracking technology in this field. There are currently five experimental studies in the field of abstract art using eye trackers as the main tool, which provide preliminary theoretical and data support for this field, but more systematic research is still the key to the development of this field.

What variables have been considered in research on the use of eye-tracker in learning abstract art?

As shown in Table 4, in the following five studies, the independent variables of the first article are color, shapes texture in abstract painting, and the dependent variable is emotional regions. The independent variable of the second article is Background information in abstract painting, and the dependent variable is Aesthetic judgment. The third article is a comparison between Abstract art and Artists versus by children and animals, and the dependent variable is Perceived difference. The fourth is a comparative study between Figurative painting and Abstract painting, and the dependent variable is Implied motion. The last article is a comparative study between Symmetry and Golden ratio in abstract painting, and the dependent variables are Pleasantness and harmony. The independent variables of the above studies are quite diverse, which shows that researchers try to understand the impact of abstract art on viewers from different visual and cognitive perspectives. The dependent variables cover emotional regions, aesthetic judgments, perceived differences, motion cues, pleasure, and harmony. It reveals that most of the current research on abstract art focuses on emotional, aesthetic, and cognitive responses. Three of the papers used a comparative research design to explore the differences between abstract art and concrete art, different creative subjects, and different composition forms.

Table 4. The variables and eye movement indices of these research

Author	Dependent variable	Independent variable	Eye movement index (EMI)
Lucia et al.(2024)	Symmetry Golden ratio	Pleasantness Harmony	Dwell time Average number of fixations
Alvarez et al.(2015)	Abstract art Artists versus by children and animals	Perceived difference	Gaze fixation Pupil dilation
Park et al. (2015)	Background information in abstract painting	Aesthetic judgment	Focus duration of attention
Castellotti et al.(2021)	Figurative painting Abstract painting	Implied motion	Pupil size expansion (in terms of fluidity)
Sartori (2014)	Color in abstract painting, Shapes in abstract painting, Texture in abstract painting	emotional regions	Fixation location Duration

What are the eye movement indicators used in the study of abstract art?

As shown in Table 4, the above studies used a total of 6 eye movement indicators (EMI): fixation location, duration, focus, expansion (in terms of fluidity, Pupil size, and dwell time. Among them, fixation location and duration are more frequently used, mainly to study the impact of visual elements (such as color, shape, texture) on emotion and aesthetics. Expansion (in terms of fluidity) and Pupil size are often used to measure emotional arousal and cognitive load, and are particularly suitable for use in studies comparing different art forms.

Discussions

This study systematically reviews the application of eye tracker technology in the field of abstract art learning and compares it with existing studies. First, existing literature reviews focus on the wide application of eye trackers in art learning (Kedziora et al., 2020; Nayak et al., 2019; Ronsenberg et al., 2022), and there are few summaries specifically for abstract art. Compared with traditional art, the non-figurative nature of abstract art places higher demands on the audience's visual perception (Alderton, 2011), and eye tracker technology provides in-depth insights into the visual focus of the viewing process by accurately capturing the audience's eye movement trajectory. (Alemda & Cagiltay, 2018) The uniqueness of this study lies in its focus on the special field of abstract art and systematically analyzing the specific applications of eye tracker technology in this field and its research trends. Second, this study is not only a description of the development of eye tracking technology, but also sorts out the variables and commonly used eye movement indicators, revealing how this technology helps understand the student's viewing patterns, emotional responses, and cognitive processes in abstract art. In addition, this study also explores the research trends of eye tracker technology in different time periods. From 2014 to 2024, the number of related studies increased year by year, especially reaching a peak from 2019 to 2021, which shows that the application of this technology in art appreciation has received more and more attention. Compared with the existing literature review, this study is the first to focus on the

application and development trend of eye trackers in abstract art learning, which not only provides direction for future research, but also provides a reference for practical applications in this field.

Conclusion

This study systematically uses the methods of systematic review and meta-analysis to sort out the research on the application of eye tracking technology in abstract art learning from 2014 to 2024. Through the analysis of five empirical studies, we summarize the research trends, current status, research variables and commonly used eye movement indicators in this field. First, the study shows that since 2014, the application of eye tracking technology in the field of abstract art learning has gradually increased, especially reaching a research peak from 2019 to 2021. Secondly, the independent variables and dependent variables involved in the study are relatively diverse. The independent variables include color, shape, symmetry, golden ratio, etc., and the dependent variables cover emotional areas, aesthetic judgments, motion cues, etc. These studies show that eye tracking technology can effectively capture the visual and emotional responses of students when viewing abstract art works. Finally, commonly used eye movement indicators such as fixation location, duration and pupil size can reflect the student's attention concentration and emotional response. The use of these indicators provides quantitative support for understanding the impact of abstract art on students.

Implications

The results of this study provide important implications for the learning and teaching of abstract art. On the one hand, this study sorted out and summarized the variables involved in the understanding of abstract art learning in the past decade of research. Current studies have shown that eye trackers play a significant role in measuring viewers' emotional, aesthetic and cognitive responses when learn abstract artworks (Castellotti et al., 2021; Sartori, 2014), which provides a reference for researchers in the field of art education. This technology can also be further applied to optimize art course design, art market analysis and visual art creation process. On the other hand, this study provides a relatively complete literature review and summarizes commonly used eye movement indicators, providing a theoretical basis and methodological guidance for subsequent related research. Finally, this study provides new research ideas for cognitive science, education, and human-computer interaction, and further promotes the integration and development of technology and art education.

Limitations

As a systematic literature review, although this study provides a comprehensive overview of the application of eye tracking technology in the field of abstract art, it still has some limitations. First, this paper only selected five major databases (Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, Web of Science, Scopus, and Taylor & Francis) for literature search. Although they cover a wide range of academic resources, relevant studies in other databases may still be missed. Second, due to the strict screening criteria, which are limited to English and empirical studies, some potentially valuable research results published in non-English environments or non-empirical studies may be excluded. Finally, despite the systematic screening through SPIDER tools, the review objects of this study are mainly focused on quantitative research, with less consideration of qualitative research, which may limit the understanding of a wider range of methods and perspectives.

Future Directions

Based on the limitations of this study, future research can be improved and expanded in the following aspects. First, subsequent systematic reviews can expand the scope of the database for literature retrieval and consider incorporating more academic resources to ensure that more comprehensive research results are covered. Second, future research should consider including non-English literature to provide a comprehensive analysis with a more global perspective. In addition, as eye tracking technology continues to develop, future research can combine quantitative and qualitative research, especially to explore more cross-field research on eye tracking and deep cognitive and emotional responses to abstract art experience. Finally, as technology and abstract art learning methods evolve, future research should continue to update the time range of the literature review to reflect the application and development trends of the latest technology in this field, and provide more dynamic and forward-looking insights for this field.

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